

Project No. 964220

Intelligent digital tools for screening of brain connectivity and dementia risk estimation in people affected by mild cognitive impairment

Deliverable 1.3

Guidelines for data management and sharing (Data Governance Plan)

WP 1 – Concept governance and requirements of the AI-Mind Connector
and Predictor

Authors	DNV, OUS, HUS, IRCCS, UCM, UCSC
Lead participant	DNV
Delivery date	24 November 2021
Dissemination level	Public
Type	Report

Version 1

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 964220

Table of Contents

REVISION HISTORY	4
ABBREVIATIONS	5
DEFINITIONS	6
PARTNER SHORT NAMES	8
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	9
1 INTRODUCTION	11
1.1. Background and context	11
1.2. The purpose and scope of this document	11
1.3. Data processing in AI-Mind	12
2 PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA WITHIN THE AI-MIND RESEARCH PROJECT	13
2.1. Contracts and agreements	13
2.1.1 AI-Mind consortium agreement	13
2.1.2 Data transfer agreement (DTA)	14
2.2. Ethical requirements	16
2.2.1 Independent ethics advisor	16
2.2.2 Ethics summary report following submission of AI-Mind from the EC	16
2.2.3 Local ethical procedures	17
2.3. The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	19
2.3.1 Chapter 2 Principles (Article 5-11)	19
2.3.2 Chapter 4 Controller and processor (Article 24-43)	20
2.3.3 Chapter 9 Provisions relating to specific processing situations	24
2.3.4 Recital 26 - Not applicable to anonymous data	24
2.3.5 Legal basis for data processing by AI-Mind’s clinical partners	25
2.4. The proposed artificial intelligence act	28
2.5. National laws	29
2.5.1 Legal obligations in Italy	29
2.5.2 Legal obligations in Finland	30
2.5.3 Legal obligations in Spain	31
2.5.4 Legal obligations in Norway	32
3 FUTURE DATA SHARING OPPORTUNITIES	32
3.1. Regulations and guidelines for sharing of data beyond AI-Mind	33
3.2. Data sharing opportunities	34
3.2.1 European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)	34

3.2.2	The Human Brain Project (HBP).....	34
3.2.3	EBRAINS	34
3.2.4	HBP: EBRAINS voucher.....	35
3.2.5	The Virtual Brain Cloud	36
4	CONCLUSIONS	36
5	ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	36
6	REFERENCES.....	37
	APPENDIX - DTA VARIATIONS BETWEEN PARTNERS.....	41

Revision History

Author(s)	Description	Date
Serena Marshall and Harry Hallock (DNV)	Draft deliverable	01.09.2021
Federico Ramírez Toraño (UCM)	Revision 1 st draft	20.09.2021
Ira Haraldsen, Lina Plataniti (OUS) Oda Bakken (OUS)	Revision 1 st draft	24.09.2021 27.09.2021
Mia Liljeström (HUS)	Revision 1 st draft	23.09.2021
Camillo Marra (IRCCS)	Revision 1 st draft	27.09.2021
Vibeke Vallevik Binz (DNV)	Revision 2 nd draft	22.10.2021
Federico Ramírez Toraño (UCM)	Revision 3 rd draft	27.10.2021
Mia Liljeström (HUS)	Revision 3 rd draft	27.10.2021
Ira Haraldsen (OUS)	Revision 3 rd draft	29.10.2021
Camillo Marra (IRCCS)	Revision 3 rd draft	03.11.2021
Richard Milne (AI-Mind ELSI external advisor)	Final review	08.11.2021
Randi Borgen (OUS)	Final review	09.11.2021
Serena Marshall (DNV)	Final version	15.11.2021
Andreia Cruz (accelCH)	Final version	22.11.2021

Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CANTAB	Cambridge Neuropsychological Test Automated Battery
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
DTA	Data Transfer Agreement
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
H2020	Horizon 2020
HBP	The Human Brain Project
MCI	Mild Cognitive Impairment
REK	The regional committee for Medical and Health Research ethics
TSD (SSD)	Tjenester for sensitive data (services for sensitive data). AI-Mind's TSD Platform is located within TSD.
UiO	Universitetet i Oslo (University of Oslo)
WP	Work Package

Definitions

Anonymisation	the process by which personal data is irreversibly altered in such a way that a data subject can no longer be identified directly or indirectly, either by the data controller alone or in collaboration with any other party (1).
Biometric data	<i>personal data resulting from specific technical processing relating to the physical, physiological or behavioural characteristics of a natural person, which allow or confirm the unique identification of that natural person (2).</i>
Consent	<i>means any freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject's wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her (2).</i>
Controller	<i>the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data; where the purposes and means of such processing are determined by Union or Member State law, the controller or the specific criteria for its nomination may be provided for by Union or Member State law (2).</i>
Cross border processing	<i>means either:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) <i>processing of personal data which takes place in the context of the activities of establishments in more than one Member State of a controller or processor in the Union where the controller or processor is established in more than one Member State: or</i> b) <i>processing of personal data which takes place in the context of the activities of a single establishment of a controller or processor in the Union, but which substantially affects or is likely to substantially affect data subjects in more than one Member State (2).</i>
Genetic data	<i>personal data relating to the inherited or acquired genetic characteristics of a natural person which give unique information about the physiology or the health of that natural person and which result, in particular, from an analysis of a biological sample from the natural person in question (2).</i>
Personal Data	<i>any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person (2)</i>
Processing	<i>any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction (2).</i>
Processor	<i>a natural or legal person, public authority, agency, or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller (2).</i>
Profiling	<i>any form of automated processing of personal data consisting of the use of personal data to evaluate certain personal aspects relating to a natural person, in particular to analyse or</i>

	<i>predict aspects concerning that natural person’s performance at work, economic situation, health, personal preferences, interests, reliability, behaviour, location or movements (2).</i>
Prospective Data	data collected from participants enrolling into the AI-Mind research study. It will consist of data from 1000 MCI patients who will undergo multiple (four time points over two years) MEG, EEG and CANTAB testing, and genetic (APOE4) and P-tau 181 tests once during the project.
Pseudonymisation	<i>the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person (2).</i>
Retrospective Data	data originating from multiple data controllers, which can be shared beyond the scope of the original project they were collected for, based on the subjects’ informed consent. In AI-Mind, retrospective data will be shared by four of the five clinical partners (excluding HUS).
Recipient	<i>a natural or legal person, public authority, agency, or another body, to which the personal data are disclosed, whether a third party or not (2).</i>
TSD Platform	Centralised secure database provisioned in TSD (located the University of Oslo, Norway), where AI-Mind data will be collated and processed.

Partner Short Names

OUS	Oslo University Hospital (Clinical data-sharing partner)
accelCH	Accelopment Schweiz AG
DNV	Det Norske Veritas
HUS	Helsinki University Hospital (Clinical data-sharing partner)
IRCCS	Scientific Institute for Research, Hospitalization and Healthcare, San Raffaele Roma (Clinical data-sharing partner)
UCM	Complutense University of Madrid (Clinical data-sharing partner)
UCSC	Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore (Clinical data-sharing partner)

Executive Summary

Background and purpose

AI-Mind is a five year EU (Horizon2020) funded project aiming to deliver innovative solutions that support early detection of dementia. Data collected from clinical partners in Norway (OUS), Italy (IRCCS/UCSC), Spain (UCM) and Finland (HUS) will be transferred to the TSD Platform in Norway and processed and analysed by the consortium's partners to create the AI-Mind tools.

This deliverable summarises the legal and ethical requirements, as well as the actions that AI-Mind's clinical partners will follow before processing data (includes collecting, storing and sharing, see Definitions). Its purpose is to give an overview of the different requirements the partners must adhere to when processing data in the scope of this research project. The report represents current knowledge and planned procedures as of November 2021.

This mapping of the complex landscape of regulatory steps necessary in the different countries shows a difference in how European countries have implemented general EU regulations into national law and how certain specific interpretations can differ. Although these variations exist, they must be (and are) effectively navigated on a country and/or clinic level to ensure that they do not act prohibitively to prevent progress within AI-Mind.

This deliverable should not be considered legal advice. Specific clinic and country requirements should always be consulted through appropriate legal avenues.

Main considerations

Processing of personal data must be carried out in concordance with local and international legislation, following signed agreements on data transfer rules. Data controllers, processors and/or providers have an obligation to inform the project participants about the collected data and what their personal data will be used for. This obligation has to be detailed and addressed depending on the situation.

EU Legal compliance

The processing of personal data must be carried out in a legally compliant way. To harmonise data privacy laws across Europe (2), since May 25th 2018, the regulation (EU) 2016/679 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (3) has been applicable to all member states (EU/EEA), and supersedes all previous rules. Digitalisation and the need to protect and share information across countries are an important part of the rationale for the GDPR.

Ethical requirements

Within AI-Mind, each country has followed their internal ethical procedures, aligning with relevant national, EU and international laws and conventions. An independent ethics advisor has been appointed, and all feedback from the EU ethical evaluation committee has been addressed.

Documentation

The Consortium Agreement between partners and the Grant Agreement between partners and the European Commission provides the foundation for content, data handling, budget, decision-making procedures, management and goals within AI-Mind. In addition to this, rules relating to data processing are formalised in the Data Transfer Agreement (DTA) between the clinical partners and Oslo University Hospital (OUS), as the coordinator and the host of all data storage within AI-Mind.

Country specific needs

Within the health sector, there is extensive national legislation for health research and other regulations of significance for processing personal data in health research. These national legislations work primarily to guide and harmonise how the Member States interprets the GDPR for the protection of personal data. It should be noted that the interpretation of how laws work together and their subsequent weighting are different between countries. This work provides a summary of these laws as they have been reported by the clinical partners in AI-Mind.

Future data processing

It is important to consider the legal and ethical requirements to enable future data processing of AI-Mind data, as well as align with current data sharing initiatives (e.g. EBRAINS) from the outset of the project. To cater to this need, the DTA must be an adaptive, renegotiable document. This will ensure that legal grounds for processing is collected and data formats for optimum sharing are decided upon.

1 Introduction

This document summarizes the legal requirements that AI-Mind partners are subject to for processing data in the scope of the project. Edits may be required at later time points as agreements around future data processing externally from AI-Mind are clarified.

1.1. Background and context

AI-Mind is a five year, EU (Horizon2020) funded project, with an allocated budget of €14 million, aiming to deliver innovative solutions that support early detection of dementia. It is composed of 15 partners from 8 countries working towards this aim. The development of data-driven solutions requires access to relevant healthcare data. The use of personal data to meet current and future health needs will only be realised if secure and efficient data processing can be achieved. Within the AI-Mind research project, collection, international transfer, storage, access to, and processing of data is required, and ethical and legal requirements must be identified and adhered to.

1.2. The purpose and scope of this document

Although the requirements to enable ethical and legal data processing should be standardised throughout countries that pledge to follow EU regulations, discrepancies and variations in interpretations, in addition to country and/or clinic-specific needs and additions, have resulted in a complex landscape.

This document serves as an overview of the complex landscape of requirements for data processing within the scope of the research project. The report provides mapping and detailing of the legal basis and other legal requirements that partners in AI-Mind must comply with, to enable lawful and ethical data processing. The input has been provided by the relevant clinical partners themselves. It is not exhaustive of all necessary details and challenges; however, it serves to raise awareness of issues that clinical institutions may have or should pay attention to, both internally and externally to AI-Mind.

This report details local data protection legislation, with information supplied from clinical partners in Norway, Italy, Spain and Finland, and over-arching European legislation. It collates the information provided by partners relating to their data sharing processes and compliance requirements within AI-Mind.

The information will support the creation of the data governance and management framework (D1.4), the subsequent implementation of the central data repository (D2.2), data injection and continuous quality assurance (D2.4).

This document is delivered within the first nine months of the AI-Mind project, in time to support the data processing needs of the different partners of AI-Mind. It represents current knowledge and planned procedures as of November 2021. Minor edits may be required at later time points as agreements around future data processing externally from AI-Mind are clarified.

Within this report, where text is *italicised* it represents information quoted directly from relevant resources.

1.3. Data processing in AI-Mind

Data collection will be conducted by the five clinical partners located in Norway, Italy, Spain and Finland. This data will be transferred to the TSD Platform in Norway (see Figure 1), and processed and analysed by the consortium's partners to create the AI-Mind tools.

Within AI-Mind, both retrospective and prospective health data derived from participants with Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) will be shared by the five clinical partners across international borders. This data will be used to build two AI tools: the AI-Mind Connector and Predictor. These tools will be developed using two AI approaches: probabilistic machine learning using brain network features and deep learning modelling based on non-processed source-reconstructed data. Evaluation through testing, bias control and assessment of predictive capabilities for MCI diagnosis will determine which models are integrated into the final AI-Mind tools.

In AI-Mind, retrospective data will be provided by four of the five clinical partners. The retrospective data will undergo anonymisation or pseudonymisation prior to inclusion in the AI-Mind project. Partners have their own responsibility to ensure that they have a legal basis for the anonymisation process of retrospective data prior to sharing it with AI-Mind.

Prospective data is being collected from participants enrolling on the AI-Mind study. It will consist of data from 1000 participants with MCI who will undergo multiple tests at a number of timepoints (baseline plus three follow-ups) throughout the study. Tests include Connectome-EEG, MEG, CANTAB (Cambridge Neuropsychological Test Automated Battery), as well as blood tests for APOE4, P-tau 181 and P-tau 217. More details about the clinical study and the data being collected are outlined in deliverable 5.1. The prospective data will be pseudonymised locally at each clinical site; personal identifiers will be removed, and the data set (per participant) will be designated with a barcode/key (EAN-8 numbering system – generated centrally at OUS and distributed to partner sites by mail, to assign locally to patients, to ensure a standardised naming procedure is followed) prior to inclusion in the TSD Platform at UiO/OUS.

The biological (blood) samples of participants in the prospective study will be stored within a central research biobank at OUS (AI-Mind Norway) for five years after the end of the project and then destroyed (in 2031). The responsibility for the management and eventual disposal of the biobank is with the AI-Mind coordinator (Ira Haraldsen) and this is communicated to participants.

EEG/MEG data will be uploaded directly into the TSD Platform from each clinical sites, CANTAB data will be uploaded from the CANTAB cloud environment directly onto the TSD Platform, in accordance with security protocols defined by TSD. Genetic data results will be directly uploaded to the TSD Platform by OUS following centralised analysis at the OUS (AI-Mind Norway) biobank.

Figure 1. Data from participants in AI-Mind is generated at five clinics and transferred to the TSD Platform, a secure centralised database for AI-Mind provisioned by TSD, who provide services for processing sensitive data. The data will be used to develop the AI-Mind connector and predictor.

2 Processing of personal data within the AI-Mind research project

The processing of personal data within a research project requires a complex interplay of ethical requirements, contractual agreements and legal regulations (including the GDPR (4) and the proposed AI Act (5)). This chapter summarises the application of these within AI-Mind, according to information provided by the clinical sites.

2.1. Contracts and agreements

This chapter summarizes the consortium agreement and the data transfer agreements that govern the processes occurring within AI-Mind.

2.1.1 AI-Mind consortium agreement

The consortium agreement for AI-Mind is based upon Regulation (EU) No 1290/2013 of the European Parliament and of the council of 11 December 2013 laying down the rules for the participation and dissemination in “Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020)”. This was agreed upon and signed by all partners with an effective date from the start date of AI-Mind (1st March 2021). Excerpts relating to data sharing protocols, ethical procedures and laws include:

- **(4.1) General principles** - *Each Party shall ensure that its work on the Project complies fully with all applicable local, government and international laws, regulations and guidelines which are effective during the period of the Grant Agreement, including those governing health and safety,*

data protection, confidentiality and where relevant, the use of human or animal subjects and good clinical practice.

- **(4.4) Ethical and regulatory approvals** - *Each Party involved in activities which require specific ethical or data treatment review, authorisations or regulation, shall perform their obligations and exercise their rights under this Consortium Agreement and the Grant Agreement in accordance with all applicable laws and regulations, and ethical guidelines, including those governing health and safety, data protection, and where relevant, any and all ethical and legal requirement regarding involvement of human subjects in research and the use of personal data and human biological material.*
- **(4.5) Transfer of material and data** - *The biological material and data shall only be transferred if it is *Needed* for the implementation of the Project and used only according to the Project specifications. The Recipient shall not be entitled to transfer of the material and data to any third Party without the Provider's prior written consent. Materials and data can be used by the Provider and Recipient only to the extent that the patient or the patient's legally authorized representatives have consent to the use for scientific purposes and the local ethical committee has permitted such use. A bilateral material transfer agreement shall specify the conditions applying to such transfer of biological material.*
- **(4.6) Processing, disclosure, and transfers of Personal Data** - *The Parties shall process Personal Data in accordance with the requirements of the GDPR as well as their respective national data protection legislation. Personal data collected for the purpose of the Project shall be processed in accordance with all the purpose, legal basis for processing, ethical approval with associated approved research protocol, other applicable regulations, including the GDPR, relevant rules and regulations, decisions by public bodies, the Project protocol, this Agreement, as well as the informed consent of the research subjects to the extent that the Project relies upon participant consent.*

Summary

As per the requirements in the Consortium Agreement, each partner is responsible for being compliant with local, national and EU laws and regulations. Each partner must obtain necessary ethical and regulatory approvals from their relevant authorities and/or committees before undertaking any part of 'the Project' requiring such approval. Limitations to data use are defined by the Consortium Agreement, national legal and ethical regulations, and the legal basis for data processing as dictated in the GDPR. Ownership remains with the data provider and the responsibility for ensuring that the data processing has a legal basis lies with the data controller. As stated in the Consortium Agreement, *each Party is an independent data controller for their own processing of personal data under this Agreement.*

2.1.2 Data transfer agreement (DTA)

Data Transfer Agreements (DTAs) describe the terms and conditions to enable data processing between different entities, with parameters for collection, transfer, storage, ownership, analysis, re-use, and destruction of data frequently defined. Specific provisions to data descriptions and controllers' obligations and rights must be met.

Within AI-Mind, DTAs have been created and signed between four of the clinical partners (providers: UCM, HUS, IRCCS, UCSC) and the fifth clinical and lead partner (recipient: OUS). The DTA states:

- (I) *The recipient is part of a group of participants (the “consortium”) that has been formed under the Horizon 2020 Call: H2020-SC1-BHC-2018-2020 for the purpose of establishing the project called “intelligent digital tools for screening of brain connectivity and dementia risk estimation in people affected by mild cognitive impairment (“AI-Mind”)” (Grant Agreement No. 964220, hereafter the “Grant Agreement”) (the “Research”), further described in the Grant Agreement Annex 1. It consists of the participants listed in the Grant Agreement (collectively the “Participants”).*
- (II) *Both existing EEG data to be used in the retrospective part of AI-Mind for AI modelling and prospective data collected as part of AI-Mind, are hereafter referred to as the “Material/Data”.*

No additional DTA is required by the other AI-Mind partners (i.e., those not collecting clinical data) as their access to the TSD Platform will be provided by the project coordinator (OUS, Ira Haraldsen).

Minor variations between the different DTAs created for each of the clinical partners are shown in Table in the Appendix (see DTA variations between partners). Examples of variations include:

- Non-limited specification to GDPR, as opposed to referring to Article 5 as an example.
- Assignment of shipping costs of biological material to the recipient.
- Governance of DTA by Spanish law and jurisdiction (UCM).
- Specification that if scientific results are published together with the data object of this agreement, such data must be published in an irreversible anonymised form to preserve participant confidentiality.

Specific DTA clauses relating to legal or ethical obligations are summarised below:

- (1.1) *Material/data will only be made available in a pseudonymised form, i.e., after all direct and indirect personal identification has been replaced by a code.*
- (1.2 ii) *Material/data (and any data derived) shall not be duplicated, transferred, distributed, or supplied to any third party...for any purpose or use without the prior written consent of the Provider.*
- (1.2 iii) *Material/data (or derivatives) shall be processed and/or used only within the recipient computational infrastructure and handled in accordance with the GDPR, including GDPR Article 5 Principles relating to the processing of personal data.*
- (2.1 viii) *Upon completion of the research, followed by request and instructions from the provider, the recipient will delete or destroy the material/data and all copies (except for a copy required for archive purposes because of compliance with applicable laws or regulations).*
- (9.2) *Entitlement to renegotiation of the DTA due to changed legislature (in accordance with the GDPR, Article 40 codes of conduct).*
- (Clause 12) *for UCM and HUS state that data protection will follow the regulations in the consortium agreement for AI-Mind.*

Other clauses from the DTA that are important for data governance will be described in deliverable 1.4 (AI-Mind data governance and data management framework).

2.2. Ethical requirements

A duty of care dictates how health research data is collected, processed, shared, and documented. A basic requirement for all phases of health research that includes people and health research data is that it must be sound, with all results documented and published. New medical knowledge of importance to humans must be shared and verifiable to check that it is not based on incorrect interpretations or deliberate manipulation. The AI-Mind study will be conducted according to the Declaration of Helsinki (6), Institutional Review Boards (21 CFR 56) (7), Obligations of Clinical investigators (21 CFR 312) (8) and Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences (CIOMS) (9) International Ethical Guidelines, which all encompass aspects of this duty of care.

This section summarizes both ethical requirements regulated through national laws and policies and the project's actions to ensure ethical processing of personal data in AI-Mind.

2.2.1 Independent ethics advisor

Following the European Commission's (EC) ethical evaluation report of the AI-Mind proposal, an independent ethics advisor, Dr. Richard Milne, has been tasked to assist the data controllers in ensuring compliance with national and EU ethical guidelines. Expertise from Dr. Milne will be utilised in reviewing deliverable 1.2 (Medical device software and AI specific regulations), deliverable 1.3 (this report on data processing), deliverable 1.6 (Best practice guidelines for AI-Mind based diagnostics) and deliverable 6.3 (HTA database), in addition to contributing advice to other work packages, where relevant.

2.2.2 Ethics summary report following submission of AI-Mind from the EC

Feedback from the EC following initial approval of the AI-Mind project was provided, some of which will be addressed in this report and deliverable 9.3 Protection of personal data (POPD) - Requirement No. 4:

- *The use of AI for diagnostic purposes raises a number of ethical issues that are not sufficiently addressed. For example, dealing with incidental findings or addressing the compliance of the developed AI tool with the EC recommendations on trustworthy AI.* This will be addressed in deliverable 1.5.
- Following a description about planned AI-Mind data processing: *Confirmation of GDPR compliance for the data transfer is needed.* This will be covered by Data transfer agreements between the relevant partners, see 2.1.2
- Data transfer agreement (DTA).
- Although the feedback from the AI-Mind consortium to the EC states that: *A DPIA will also be implemented*, this will be or has been done at the discretion of the different clinics, as they assess the risk involved, see 2.3.2.3 Article 35 Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA).

For the POPD, in addition to the tasks and deliverables that were previously stated in the AI-Mind proposal, the feedback states the following compulsory requirements must be submitted or conveyed to participants:

1. *The beneficiary **must check** if special derogations pertaining to the rights of data subjects or the processing of genetic, biometric and/or health data have been established under the national legislation of the country where the research takes place and **submit a declaration of compliance***

with the respective national legal framework(s). This is addressed in Deliverable 9.3 (see the section on National and EU legislation).

2. *The host institution must confirm that it has appointed a Data Protection Officer.* This is addressed in Deliverable 9.3.
3. *A description of the technical and organisational measures that will be implemented to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subjects/research participants **must be submitted as a deliverable.*** This is addressed in this Deliverable 1.3 (see the section on Ethical requirements, the GDPR and National Laws).
4. *A description of the security measures that will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to personal data or the equipment used for processing **must be submitted as a deliverable.*** This is addressed in Deliverable 1.4 (see the section on Cybersecurity and Technology and tools).
5. *Description of the anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques that will be implemented **must be submitted as a deliverable.*** This will be addressed in Deliverable 9.4.
6. *The research involves profiling; therefore, the beneficiary **must provide explanation** of how the data subjects will be informed of the existence of the profiling, its possible consequences and how their fundamental rights will be safeguarded.* This will be addressed in Deliverable 9.4.

2.2.3 Local ethical procedures

Each clinical partner has its own local procedures for ensuring that the project adheres to the required ethical standard for protecting participants in their country. Local ethical approval has been obtained by each clinical partner prior to the transfer of retrospective data to the TSD Platform or collection of prospective data.

2.2.3.1 Procedure in Italy

The Italian ministerial decree of February 8, 2013 (10) defines Ethic Committees as *independent bodies responsible for ensuring the rights, safety and well-being of subjects enrolled in clinical studies*, providing a public guarantee of protection by offering a *scientific, ethical and methodological* evaluation of clinical trials.

Ethical approval of the AI-Mind project requires review by the regional ethics committee. Along the process to obtain the approval, it has been noted that there is a necessity to specify details regarding future research and/or data use, as generalised statements will not be acceptable.

2.2.3.2 Procedure in Finland

In Finland, the regional ethics committee that must act in each hospital district with a university providing medical education shall monitor, guide and evaluate the handling of matters pertaining to research ethics in its region (see the Medical Research Act Code 488/1999 (11) chapter 4 Ethics committees, section 16 (794/2010) *Regional and national ethics committee*, also see 2.5.2 Legal obligations in Finland). This committee must provide prior evaluation and opinions on the AI-Mind research project (section 17 794/2010): *For the purposes of delivering the opinion, the committee shall examine whether the research plan has taken account of the provisions and regulations regarding medical research laid down in this Act and other law and the provisions laid down in virtue of it. In its opinions, the ethics committee shall give its reasoned view on whether or not the research is ethically acceptable* (11).

Obtaining ethical approval was delayed to October 2021 as clarification around blood sampling and biobanks, including details about the responsible person and location, was required. In addition, a new

simplified procedure for obtaining ethical approval was introduced in early 2021, and it was preferable to apply for ethical approval in accordance with the new guidelines. A DPIA was integrated as a standard into the updated ethics procedures. The application for ethical approval was submitted on September 9, and final ethical approval was obtained on October 14 after minor modifications.

2.2.3.3 Procedure in Spain

In Spain, Law 14/2007 of Biomedical Research dictates that the Ethics Committees for Investigation (CEI) corresponding to each respective clinical centre must evaluate all biomedical research involving human interventions or the use of their biological samples (12).

Ethical approval for the AI-Mind project was sought via an extension of a previous ethics agreement, with requirements to edit due to the necessity for international data sharing. Initial problems identified along the ethical approval process by the Delegada de Protección de Datos (data protection officer) include examples such as that:

- Measures must be incorporated to ensure that publication of sensitive data containing results are carried out in an irreversibly anonymised manner.
- The Norwegian jurisdiction is unknown to the relevant legal authority in Spain; therefore, disputes must be submitted to the Spanish jurisdiction, regardless of the competence of the appropriate Data Protection Control Authority.
- To enable AI-Mind data reuse, not covered by the initial consent, intent of new use must be published in an easily accessible place on the corporate website, and if possible, notify the existence of this information by electronic means to those affected; all with the approval of the research ethics committee.
- Statements relating to plans to be compliant with the GDPR, pseudonymisation and re-identification prevention, confidentiality and security are not sufficient, specific guarantees must be addressed.

2.2.3.4 Procedure in Norway

In Norway, the Health Research Act §10 (13) (see section 2.5.4 Legal obligations in Norway) regulates the requirement and expectations of regional committees for Medical and Health Research Ethics (REK). REKs are obligated to apply ethical standards that supplement the legal standards ensuing from the Health Research Act and other law rules (14).

REK assessed the AI-Mind project and has approved the use of retrospective data and collection of prospective data. Initial approval was given on 21st December 2020. On the 3rd February 2021, REK requested two compulsory modifications as pre-conditions for approval:

- The first concerns feedback to participants. REK acknowledge that although the risk to participants is low, the potential gain to them from their time invested in additional surveys should be repaid through the provision of feedback from their individual results (even where analysis finds negative findings i.e., a person not at risk)
- The second is a modification of the information sheet provided to participants to contain both texts and links to appropriate Norwegian text.

Resubmission for approval was initiated on 30th March 2021, and full approval was given on 13th April 2021, after evidence that conditions were (or will be) complied with. REK state that 'the permit is granted on the condition that the project is carried out as described in the application' in accordance with the provisions made by the Health Research Act.

The permit from REK is valid until 31.12.2030. For documentation reasons, the information must be kept until 31.12.2035. The research file must be stored separately in a key and information file. The information must then be deleted or anonymised no later than one and a half years from this date.

In addition to this, the REK committee approved the establishment of a specific AI-Mind research biobank to be used by all participating clinical partners. If the research biobank is terminated, closed down or taken over by others, a REK permit must be applied for in accordance with the Health Research Act § 30 (13) (see section 2.5.4 Legal obligations in Norway).

2.3. The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

The regulation (EU) 2016/679 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (3) entered into force May 25th 2018, and superseded the Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC (15). The aim is to harmonise data privacy laws throughout the EU. The GDPR applies directly to all member states within the EU and the EEA, and has been interpreted and applied into their national laws accordingly. Thus, it serves as a common legal reference for health research and health information data processing across all involved parties in AI-Mind. However, it should be noted that the GDPR also contains several opportunities for the member states to lay down additional national rules on certain aspects (Article 6 (2), Article 9 (4)), e.g. when it comes to the processing of personal data for the purposes of scientific research and for the purposes of providing health services. This means that the AI-Mind partners may have additional national regulations to consider as well.

In this chapter, articles in the GDPR particularly relevant to AI-Mind's data processing will be highlighted and discussed. How AI-Mind intends to comply with them is illustrated in [blue text](#).

2.3.1 Chapter 2 Principles (Article 5-11)

Chapter 2 details the principles of the GDPR (16):

2.3.1.1 Article 5 - Principles relating to processing of personal data

Article 5 (1) of the GDPR is concerned with the processing of personal data, with an emphasis on (a) lawfulness, fairness and transparency, (b) processing only according to specified purpose (purpose limitation) (c) limitation to what is required (data minimisation) (e) limitation and safeguarding of data and (f) processed in a manner that ensures security (integrity and confidentiality).

Article 5 (2) assigns responsibility for these principles (Article 5 (1) (a-f) to the data controllers ([in AI-Mind, all clinical partners are assigned as independent data controllers](#)), and compliance with these must be demonstratable.

2.3.1.2 Article 6 – Lawfulness of processing

Article 6 (1) (a-f) of the GDPR details the different requirements for legal processing. A minimum of one requirement must be fulfilled for processing to occur, and these include (a) consent (for one or more specified purposes), (b) performance of a contract, (c) legal obligation, (d) protection of vital interests, (e) protection of public interest or (f) legitimate interest.

Article 6 (2) states that Member States may maintain or introduce more specific provisions to adapt the application of the rules of this Regulation with regard to processing for compliance with points (c) and (e) of paragraph 1 by determining more precisely specific requirements for the processing and other measures to ensure lawful and fair processing.

Article 6 (4) is relevant to the further processing of the data and covers the processing of data for purposes other than that which was conveyed to the participant and agreed to within their consent.

In the case of article 6 (4), the controller (OUS, or any of the clinics that collect and store their participant data) must ascertain whether this new processing is compatible with the purpose for which the personal data was initially collected, taking into account (a-e) links, context, nature, consequence and existence of safeguards.

2.3.1.3 Article 7 – Conditions for consent

For clinical partners for which the legal basis for the processing of data within AI-Mind is based on consent (Article 6 (1) (a)), specific requirements relating to the consent must be addressed:

1. *The controller shall be able to demonstrate that the data subject has consented to processing of his or her personal data.*
2. *If consent is collected within documentation pertaining to other matters, the request for consent shall be presented in a manner which is clearly distinguishable from the other matters, in an intelligible and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language.*
3. *Withdrawal: 1) consent can be withdrawn at any time, 2) shall not affect the lawful processing based on consent prior to withdrawal, 3) participant shall be informed of withdrawal options prior to the consent, and 4) to withdraw consent shall be as easy as to consent.*
4. *Consent must be freely given, and the provision of usual service given is not conditional on consent.*

Following the EC ethical requirements, the national consent documents are supplemented with an “information sheet” designed by the leading Norwegian partner and made available in all countries in an understandable language to all participants. As such, participating AI-Mind clinical partners have a responsibility to ensure that their native consents encompass the AI-Mind determined information, the GDPR designations, and meet their specific needs.

2.3.1.4 Article 9 – Processing of special categories of personal data

Article 9 (1) of the GDPR prohibits specific processing of personal data (such as genetic data, biometric data, data concerning health) unless any of the listed exceptions apply e.g. (2) (a) *the participant has given explicit consent for processing to the specified purpose(s)*, (i) *processing is necessary for reasons of public interest in the area of public health or* (j) *processing is necessary for scientific research purposes in accordance with Article 89 (which shall be proportionate to the aim pursued, respect the essence of the right to data protection and provide for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the fundamental rights and the interests of the data subject)*

Article 9 (4) states that member states may maintain or introduce further conditions, including limitations, with regard to the processing of genetic data, biometric data or data concerning health.

Processing of AI-Mind data is in accordance with Article 9 (1) and (2), and additional national requirements for data processing will be discussed below (2.5 National laws).

2.3.2 Chapter 4 Controller and processor (Article 24-43)

Chapter 4 of the GDPR details general obligations (section 1), security of personal data (section 2), data protection impact assessment (section 3, see 2.3.2.3 Article 35 Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) below), data protection officer (DPO) (section 4, see 2.3.2.4 below) and codes of conduct and certification (17).

Within AI-Mind, each partner is considered an independent data controller and is independently responsible for processing their own data in relation to AI-Mind in their own institutions. This means that the rights and obligations of the data controller arising from the GDPR are the responsibility of each institution that processes (personal) data in connection with the research project.

As the host institution, OUS has an additional role compared to the other data controllers; facilitating storage of all the collected data (including data transferred from the other partners) on a technical and secure platform (TSD Platform) that the other partners shall have access to in order to carry out the research. After the data has been transferred to the TSD Platform, OUS will act as the data controller for the transferred data in accordance with the research protocol, the Consortium Agreement, the Data Transfer Agreements, and the GDPR. OUS has entered into a data processing agreement with TSD.

2.3.2.1 Article 30 Security of processing

Article 30 (1) states that the controller and each processor (plus where applicable their representatives) are obligated to maintain records of relevant contact details, processing activities or categories of processing activities carried out on personal data by the controller or processor, respectively.

The coordinator (OUS) has consulted with the AI-Mind DPO (see 2.3.2.4) to receive information and advice regarding compliance with Article 30.

2.3.2.2 Article 32 Security of processing

Section 2 details the obligations of the controller and processor with respect to the security of processing, (Article 33) procedures for notification of personal data breach and (Article 34) communication of subsequent data breach to the data subject.

Article 32 works in tandem with (Article 5 (1) (f)) '*integrity and confidentiality*' and states;

Taking into account the state of the art, the costs of implementation and the nature, scope, context and purposes of processing as well as the risk of varying likelihood and severity for the rights and freedoms of natural persons, the controller and the processor shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure a level of security appropriate to the risk, including inter alia as appropriate:

- a) *the pseudonymisation and encryption of personal data;*
- b) *the ability to ensure the ongoing confidentiality, integrity, availability and resilience of processing systems and services;*
- c) *the ability to restore the availability and access to personal data in a timely manner in the event of a physical or technical incident;*
- d) *a process for regularly testing, assessing, and evaluating the effectiveness of technical and organisational measures for ensuring the security of the processing (3).*

Additional considerations must be made to the (2) risks presented by processing *in particular from accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure of, or access to personal data transmitted, stored, or otherwise processed*. Compliance to a (3) code of conduct could be used to demonstrate acknowledgement of risk and subsequent security requirements.

Data storage and security within AI-Mind is the responsibility of each partner locally and the responsibility of TSD for the TSD Platform where all data will be transferred to and processed within. The TSD Platform is risk assessed and in compliance with technical and organisational requirement for processing data for scientific purposes. UiO (where TSD is located) and OUS have a data processing agreement between them for the use of the platform.

2.3.2.3 Article 35 Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA)

The necessity for a DPIA can be determined following the flow chart in Figure 2, with the first determinant being whether the processing of data *is likely to result in high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons*. Article 35 (1) GDPR requires data controllers to ensure the protection of personal data, consult with the DPO and if there is high risk; a risk assessment (DPIA) for the processing activity is required.

Figure 2 Determining the necessity for a DPIA (adapted from (19))

The European data protection board, replacing the article 29 working party, endorsed their DPIA high processing risk guidelines (Regulation 2016/679) (19). It is a process for building and demonstrating compliance through a process designed to describe the processing, assess its necessity and proportionality and help manage the risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons resulting from the processing of personal data by assessing them and determining the measures to address them.

According to GDPR, non-compliance with DPIA requirements can result in administrative fines of up to €10 million, and therefore the consistent interpretation of the (non-limited) circumstances in which a DPIA is mandatory (Article 35 (3)) have been published.

The risk and therefore requirement for a DPIA has been assessed at the beginning of the project (approximately month three) by each of the clinical partners and their respective legal offices/DPOs and the conclusions from each country for processing data within AI-Mind to the TSD Platform is summarised in

Table 1.

Table 1 DPIA necessity for sharing of AI-Mind research data to the TSD Platform for each country

Country	DPIA required for sharing to the TSD Platform	Reason given
Italy (UCSC/IRCCS)	No	It is not anticipated that the processing of anonymised and pseudonymised personal data will entail specific risks to the rights and freedoms of the participants.
Finland (HUS)	Yes	A DPIA is integrated into the ethical approval process and is therefore carried out as standard.
Spain (UCM)	No	It is not expected that the processing of personal data will entail specific risks to the rights and freedoms of the participants.
Norway (OUS)	No	The risk to participants is low and data storage is secure within the TSD Platform. Although processing occurs on special categories of data on a large scale, the retrospective data is considered anonymised (mitigated risk to identification) and use of prospective data is based on the participants consent (or other legal avenues under GDPR), is de-identified and in compliance with general appropriate safety measures.

Despite these conclusions, the coordinator (OUS with the DPO) has decided to carry out a DPIA assessment on behalf of OUS. This has been decided at approximately month six of the project following successful applications to participate in EBRAINS (see 3.2.3 EBRAINS, www.healthdatacloud.eu). This DPIA assessment will encompass the entire project, the data sets and all data processing operations, however, AI-Mind is not an institution with compliance responsibilities according to GDPR, as such compliance is each institution’s responsibility. However, assessment by the leading centre for the research project may be considered or adopted for the whole project, effectively preventing the necessity for work duplication at the different clinical sites.

2.3.2.4 Article 38 Position of the DPO and Article 39 Tasks of the DPO

In accordance with Article 38, the controller and the processor shall (1) ensure that the DPO is involved, properly and in a timely manner, in all issues related to the protection of personal data and (2) shall support the tasks they are required to do.

The DPO shall (Article 39. GDPR) (1) (a) inform and advise the data controller or the processor, (b) monitor compliance with the GDPR (c) advise regarding the necessity for and monitoring of a DPIA (see below), (d) cooperate with the supervisory authority and (e) act as the contact point for the supervisory authority (with respect to processing and other appropriate matters).

A project DPO has been appointed at OUS. The DPO at OUS gives advice and recommendations to the institution (i.e. the data controller) about the interpretation or application of the data protection rules;

however, it is the institution that is responsible for complying with the GDPR and make decisions accordingly.

The same applies to all partners in AI-Mind; as independent data controllers, each clinical partner is responsible for consulting the DPO at their own institutions when required. This might be necessary not only to comply with the GDPR, but also to comply with country/clinic specific data protection requirements.

For the sake of OUS as a host institution, the DPO at OUS recommends that the AI-Mind project is carried out under the assumption of the following:

1. *The Data controller is Oslo University Hospital, represented by the CEO.*
2. *Processing of personal data in the project is in accordance with and within the purpose specified in the notification form.*
3. *Data is stored as specified in the notification.*
4. *Documents linking de-identified data with personal data shall be stored as indicated in the notification form.*
5. *The study is based on each participant's consent.* This refers to participation in the research project being based on consent and is not a reference to consent to data processing.
6. *Data shall be deleted or anonymised at project completion by cross-deleted list and any other identification possibilities in the database are removed.*
7. *When the purpose of the register is fulfilled, a notification shall be sent to the Data Protection Officer to confirm the deletion.*

2.3.3 Chapter 9 Provisions relating to specific processing situations

Chapter 9 of the GDPR addresses processing in specific use cases e.g. (Article 86) public access to official documents, (Article 87) national ID numbers and (Article 88) in employment (20).

2.3.3.1 Article 89 Safeguards and derogations relating to processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes

In accordance with Article 89 (1) ¹Processing for archiving purposes in scientific research purposes *shall be subject to appropriate safeguards, in accordance with this Regulation, for the rights and freedoms of the data subject.* ²*Those safeguards shall ensure that technical and organisational measures are in place* (with respect for the principle of data minimisation). ³Pseudonymisation may be appropriate or ⁴*Where those purposes can be fulfilled by further processing which does not permit or no longer permits the identification of data subjects, those purposes shall be fulfilled in that manner* (ie using anonymous data).

As discussed in 2.2 Ethical requirements, the data collected and processed in the TSD Platform for the purposes of AI-Mind has been given authorisation from OUS' REK for archiving until 31.12.2035. The data must then be deleted or anonymised no later than one and a half years from this date. Any change has to be formally reported and approved by DPOs and Ethical committees.

2.3.4 Recital 26 - Not applicable to anonymous data

Recital 26 of the GDPR (21) states that *the principles of data protection should apply to any information concerning an identified or identifiable natural person. Personal data which have undergone*

pseudonymisation, which could be attributed to a natural person by the use of additional information should be considered to be information on an identifiable natural person.

To determine whether a natural person is identifiable, it is necessary to ascertain whether re-identification is *reasonably likely* to be possible when considering objective factors such as cost and time investment for reidentification and available state of the art technology at the time of processing. *The principles of data protection should therefore not apply to anonymous information, namely, information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or to personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable.*

Thus all AI-Mind pseudonymised prospective and retrospective data is regulated by the GDPR, however, the regulation does not concern the processing of AI-Mind anonymous retrospective data. Regardless of this, the anonymised data will be stored within the TSD Platform and subject to data protection similar to that for the pseudonymised data, as detailed in the AI-Mind data governance and management framework (D1.4).

2.3.5 Legal basis for data processing by AI-Mind's clinical partners

Participants in the AI-Mind research project are notified in the informed consent forms about which legal avenues are used to support processing of their data. The informed consent forms for each clinic were submitted in the confidential deliverable 9.1 – Human beings – Requirement No. 2, where a procedure for documenting amendments to consent forms is also described.

The approved information sheet that all consent documents in AI-Mind should be based on includes:

- In accordance with the general data protection regulation (GDPR), the Data Protection Officer and coordinator are responsible for ensuring that all processing of your personal data is in accordance with current national and European regulations as mentioned (described) above.
- The data-sharing server satisfies the requirements for data security in accordance with the EU Privacy Regulation (also known as the GDPR).
- The national insurances are covered by each national Patient Injuries Act and the Product Liability Act.
- Consent to participate in the research project: *I consent to participating in the research project and that my personal data concerning health and biological material can be used as described above (signature).*

In line with the most recent guidelines and recommendations from the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) (22,23), consent for data processing may not be an appropriate legal basis in research projects where it can be constituted that there is an imbalance between the data controller and the data subject – which very often will be the case in health research projects (24).

In this case, consent to participate in the research is still obtained in accordance with the requirements for conducting research on humans that follow from the Declaration of Helsinki and the Oviedo Convention, in addition to requirements in national law that research on humans shall be based on consent from the participants. The consent to participate in a research project is not to be confused with consent to process personal data according to the GDPR. This consent does not constitute the legal basis in terms of the GDPR, but is an ethical and legal requirement when conducting research on humans. It does, however, serve as an additional safeguard in order to fulfil the data and research subjects' rights to information both about the research and about the data processing, and to comply with Article 89 (1) in

the GDPR. The stated legal bases for data processing provided to participants on each country’s informed consent documents is provided in table 2.

Within AI-Mind some partners have based their processing on consent (cf. article 6 (1) (a) and article 9 (1) (a)), while others have based it on Article 6 (1) (c), Article 6 (1) (e), Article 9 (1) (j) and Article 9 (2) (i). Each/any partner in the project (or joining the project in the future) has to consider and define the legal basis for their processing according to the GDPR Article 6 and Article 9.

Table 2 The stated legal bases for data processing provided to participants on each country’s informed consent documents.

Clinic/country	Stated legal basis for data processing
<p>IRCSS and UCSC, Italy (English consent)</p>	<p>The study protocol, which covers the procedures that the researchers will follow for this study, has been drawn up in accordance with the standards of good clinical practice of the European Union and the current version of the Declaration of Helsinki. It has also been approved by the ethics committee of IRCSS San Raffaele Roma.</p> <p>The TSD solution meets the data security requirements in accordance with the European Privacy Regulation. At the same time, all transmission and sharing of data will be subject to different agreements approved by the European Union.</p> <p>National insurance coverage for this study is provided by the Accident Act and the Product Liability Act.</p> <p>Consent to participate in the research project: I therefore freely accept to participate in this study, having fully understood what this involves, and any risks and benefits linked to such participation.</p>
<p>IRCSS and UCSC, Italy (Italian consent)</p>	<p>National insurance coverage for this study is provided by the Accident Act and Product Liability Act.</p> <p>The TSD solution meets the data security requirements in accordance with the European Privacy Regulation. At the same time, all transmission and sharing of data will be subject to different agreements approved by the European Union.</p> <p>The study protocol proposed to you has been drawn up in accordance with the Standards of Good Clinical Practice of the European Union and the current revision of the Declaration of Helsinki. It has also been approved by the Ethics Committee of this structure.</p> <p>Consent to participate in the research project: I therefore freely accept to participate in the trial, having fully understood the meaning of the request and having understood the risks and benefits that are involved.</p>
<p>HUS, Finland</p>	<p>The HUS Research Ethics Committee has granted ethical permission for the research project.</p> <p>Finnish legislation on the protection of research and personal data is applied.</p> <p>Where such processing is necessary for the protection of public health:</p>

	<p>Articles 6 (1) (e) and Article 9 (2) (i)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) to ascertain or evaluate the purpose, performance, properties, effects or effectiveness of the matter under investigation or to ensure its quality, efficacy or safety; or 2) to ensure the safety of subjects or other persons. <p>If such processing is necessary:</p> <p>Article 6 (1) (c) and Article 9 (2) (i)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) to comply with the obligation to report an adverse event or effect or other safety-related reporting obligation; 2) in order to comply with any other notification or investigation obligation related to the investigation or the obligation related to the preservation of information or documents; or 3) in order to comply with the obligation related to the disclosure of information provided to the authority. <p>Section 6 (2) for adaption, through introduction of specific provisions to ensure member state compliance of Article 6 (1) (c) and (e).</p> <p>HUS has insured the study participants in accordance with the Patient Insurance Act.</p> <p>You have the right to lodge a complaint, in particular with the supervisory authority of your place of residence or employment, if you consider that the processing of personal data infringes the general EU data protection regulation (EU) 2016/679.</p> <p>Consent to participate in the research project: By signing, I confirm my participation in this study and voluntarily agree to be a research subject.</p>
<p>UCM, Spain</p>	<p>All information (personal, clinical, and data from research with biological or neuroimaging material) collected on your behalf will be treated in accordance with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the (superseded) Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council, of 24th October 1995 and • Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of April 27, 2016 (the GDPR) for the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data. • Organic Law 3/2018, of December 5, for Protection of Personal Data and guarantee of digital rights <p>Stated compliance was given with the Declaration of Helsinki of the World Medical Association (64th General Assembly, Fortaleza, Brazil, October 2013), and the Oviedo Convention relative to Human Rights and Biomedicine (Council of Europe, 1997).</p> <p>National laws quoted included the</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic Law 41/2002 regulating patient autonomy and rights and

	<p>obligations regarding information and clinical documentation,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biomedical Research Law 14/2007 • General Public Health Law 33 / 2011, of October 4, • Royal Decree 1716/2011, of November 18, which establishes the basic requirements for authorization and operation of biobanks for the purposes of biomedical research and treatment of biological samples of human origin <p>Consent to participate in the research project is given through itemised consent for specific clauses, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disclosure of information to parties described • Future research and secondary uses (within a related field) • Performance of genetic analysis • Storage of biological materials for future research • Read and fully understood consent • Agree to participate under the terms provided
<p>OUS, Norway</p>	<p>The data-sharing server satisfies the requirements for data security in accordance with the EU Privacy Regulation (also known as the GDPR).</p> <p>The project management will also, in consultation with the hospital's Privacy Officer, ensure that your personal information is handled in accordance with European and national regulations.</p> <p>This study is covered by the National Insurance of Patient Injuries Act and the Product Liability Act.</p> <p>The National Committee for Medical and Health Research Ethics has reviewed and approved this research project [REK (204084/2021)] and European regulations as mentioned above.</p> <p>In accordance with the general data protection ordinance, the person responsible for processing (name), Oslo University Hospital, Norway and the international project coordinator (name) are responsible for ensuring that all processing of your personal data is in accordance with current national and European regulations mentioned above.</p> <p>Consent to participate in the research project: I agree to allow the projects to make my personal information and my biological materials use as described (signature)</p> <p>Opt-out of return of results: I do not want my GP nor myself to receive information about my results from this study (signature)</p>

2.4. The proposed artificial intelligence act

Similarly to the GDPR, the European Commission has created a proposal titled 'Laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (artificial intelligence act) and amending certain union legislative acts' (5),

published on the 21st April 2021. This proposal aims to implement the development of an ecosystem of trust by proposing a legal framework for trustworthy AI (deliverable 1.2).

When developing AI, certain requirements to the quality of data must be taken into account. Article 10 *Data and data governance* provides a quality-criteria framework for training, validation and testing data sets involved in the training of models in high-risk AI systems. These *data sets shall be subject to appropriate data governance and management practices* concerning (2(b)) data collection, (2(c)) relevant data preparation processing operations (including aggregation), (2(e)) a prior assessment of the availability, quantity and suitability of the data sets that are needed, (2(f)) examination of possible biases and (2(g)) identification and methods to address data gaps or shortcomings.

Quality criteria described for the training, validation and testing data sets describe that they shall be (3) *relevant, representative, free of errors and complete*, and (4) *take into account the characteristics or elements that are particular to the specific geographical, behavioural or functional setting within which the high risk AI system is intended to be used*.

To the extent that it is strictly necessary for the purposes of ensuring bias monitoring, special categories of personal data referred to in Article 9(1) of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (the GDPR), Article 10 of Directive (EU) 2016/680 (concerned with the protection of personal data during processing by competent authorities (25)) and Article 10(1) of Regulation (EU) 2018/1725 (concerned with the protection of personal data during processing by the Union (26)) may be processed (5). This is *subject to appropriate safeguards for the fundamental rights and freedoms of natural persons, including technical limitations on the re-use and use of state-of-the-art security and privacy-preserving measures, such as pseudonymisation or encryption where anonymisation may significantly affect the purpose pursued*.

The proposed rules in the AI-Act will be enforced through a governance system at the Member States level, building on already existing structures, and a cooperation mechanism at the Union level with the establishment of a European Artificial Intelligence Board.

2.5. National laws

In addition to the GDPR and the proposed AI-Act, countries have their own extensive national legal obligations related to personal data protection. These national legislations work primarily to guide and harmonise how the GDPR is interpreted by the Member States for the protection of personal data. The interpretation of how these laws work together and their subsequent weighting are different between countries. This section summarises information provided by clinical partners about their national laws. The list is non-exhaustive, thus more comprehensive information should be sought from national authorities.

2.5.1 Legal obligations in Italy

Additional laws for data protection for both prospective and retrospective data that IRCCS/UCSC must consult include:

- Privacy Code 196/2003 (27) as amended by Legislative Decree 101/2018 (28), which entered into force on 19th September 2018. Its' goal is to harmonise aspects that the GDPR delegates to the Member States for the protection of personal data. This decree set forth transitional provisions to regulate the transition at a national level from the pre-GDPR regime to the future regime. Of relevance, *the Italian Data Protection Authority will issue, on a two-year basis, specific safety measures (including pseudonymisation, encryption, minimisation, etc.) regarding the processing of*

biometric data, genetic data, and health-related data aimed at safeguarding the rights of the data subjects.

- In particular, within the Privacy Code 196/2003 (Chapter III) Processing for Statistical or Scientific purposes - section 104 (Scope of Application and Identification Data for Statistical or Scientific Purposes), Section 105 (Processing Arrangements), Section 106 (Codes of Conduct and Professional Practice) and Section 110 (Medical, Biomedical and Epidemiological Research) were noted as being particularly relevant to data processing in AI-Mind.
- Guidelines from the European Data Protection Board (general guidelines, recommendations, and best practices) to clarify and promote a common understanding and implementation of EU data protection laws (such as the GDPR and the proposed Data Governance Act) are published on a continual basis and will be considered.

No additional laws, aside from emphasised specific reference to the GDPR Article 4 (11) definition for consent for data protection for both prospective and retrospective data processing, is required by IRCCS/UCSC. For future use and/or transfer to third parties not included in the clinical trial, or for inclusion in scientific publications, both the prospective and retrospective data must be aggregated and anonymous.

2.5.2 Legal obligations in Finland

Additional laws for data protection for both prospective and retrospective data that HUS must consult include:

- Medical Research Act, Code 488/1999 (29), which entered into force 1st November 1999. It offers general conditions governing medical research (section 3 295/2004). In particular, People in charge of research (section 5) - detailing the necessity for competent professional staff and Consent of research subjects (section 6 295/2004) – detailing that informed voluntary consent should be obtained in writing with participants having the right to withdraw at any time.
- Data Protection Act 1050/2018, which entered into force 5th December 2018, to harmonise and add to the protection of personal data delegated by the GDPR (30). Of relevance to AI-Mind data use, this act details legal bases for data processing (chapter 2), supervisory authorities (Chapter 3) and derogations for scientific research (chapter 5 § 31).

For obtaining health records and data for secondary purposes, HUS must consult the:

- Act on the Status and Rights of Patients 785/1992, issued on the 17th August 1992 (31). Under this Act, confidential patient records can be shared with that patient's consent. This act applies when records are sought from a single source.
- Secondary Use of Health and Social Data Act (2019) (32). This act aligns with the GDPR and aims to facilitate effective and safe processing of personal data for steering, supervision, research, statistics, and developments in the health sector. The Secondary Use act applies when collating data from several controllers and is aided by the creation of a new centralised permissions authority (www.findata.fi), which grants permission, compiles the data, and makes it available in a limited capacity within a secure processing environment.

To access and share data generated for use by AI-Mind, a data transfer agreement (DTA) must be created and ratified between the data provider and controller, and the requirements detailed in the Medical Research Act and Data Protection Act (discussed above) must be complied with. Details about the DTA can be found in 2.1.2

Data transfer agreement (DTA). In compliance with Section 6 (295/2004) of the Medical Research Act (see above), future data use for purposes that vary from that with which the data was originally collected and conveyed to the participant may need renewed consent from each of the participants. In compliance with the Act on Secondary Use of Health and Social Data, the reuse of health data, particularly MR images that have been collected for clinical use, may need to be presented to the Committee for secondary use of health and social data at Helsinki University Hospital. No problems are anticipated with this process, as reuse should be permitted for research purposes.

2.5.3 Legal obligations in Spain

Additional laws for biological samples that will be consulted and referred to by UCM include:

- Spanish Law 14/2007, of July 3, on Biomedical Research (12) - (Article 1 (1)) *The object of this Law, with full respect towards human dignity and identity and the inherent rights of a person, is the regulation of biomedical research, including (c) The handling of biological samples, (d) The storage and movement of biological samples and (2) the undertaking of genetic analysis and the processing of genetic data of a personal nature.* Article 4 is concerned with informed consent and, similarly to OUS ethic requirements, (5) the right to be informed about data obtained in the course of biomedical research. Other relevant articles include (Article 5) Protection of personal data and guarantees of confidentiality, (Article 9) Limits on genetic analysis and (Article 12) Research Ethics Committees.
- Spanish Royal Decree 1716/2011, of November 18 (33), establishing the basic requirements of authorization and functioning of biobanks for biomedical research and the management of human biological samples and regulating the functioning and organization of the National Registry of Biobanks for biomedical research (available in Spanish).
- Spanish Basic Law 41/2002 (34), regulating autonomy of the patient and the rights and obligations regarding clinical information and documentation
- General Public Health Law 33/2011, of October 4th (35), establishes the legal bases that support the actions of coordination and cooperation of public administrations in the field of public health.

Additional laws for data protection for both prospective and retrospective data sharing, processing and future use that will be consulted and referred to by UCM include:

- Spanish Organic Law 3/2018, of December 5, on Data Protection and Guarantee of Digital Rights. This Law adapts the EU GDPR to Spanish legislation and repeals the previous Organic Law 15/1999 (36).

For compliance: *Specifically, UCM needs an explicit consent from each participant for the use of their personal data for purposes related to the project. The manager of the data (in this case the UCM lab) must guarantee the confidentiality and protection of the personal data. In addition, the participant must consent to the sharing of their data with international parties.*

2.5.4 Legal obligations in Norway

Additional laws for data protection for both prospective and retrospective data that AI-Mind must be compliant with include:

- The Health Research Act (*No.:* helseforskningsloven) (13) - The Health Research Act entered into force on 1st July 2009 and regulates medical and health research on humans, human biological material or health information. Specific provisions of interest that are relevant to AI-Mind may include Requirements for the organisation and practice of medical and health research (chapter 2), Consent (chapter 4), Research biobanks and research involving human biological material (chapter 6) and Research on health information (chapter 7). §10 concerns the application for prior approval of a research project to the relevant regional committee for medical and health research ethics (REK), who will then assess whether the proposed project meets the requirements detailed within the Health Research Act.
- The Research Ethics Act (*No.:* forskningsetikkloven) (37) - The Research Ethics Act entered into force on 1st May 2017 and regulates research, researchers and research institutes (both public and private). § 10 concerns the Ministry appointing members of the medical and health research ethics committee, with competence in relevant research disciplines, ethics, and law, to assess research proposals.

National guidelines such as the Norwegian Directorate of Health's guide for 'Privacy and information security in research projects within the health and care sector' will also be relevant, but note that this document is not legally binding. Adoption of required technical standards and interoperability requirements must be established and enabled to ensure the future use of the AI-Mind data for the benefit of patients.

3 Future data sharing opportunities

Towards European Health Data Space (TEHDAS) has stated, in their milestone 5.7 Why health is a special case for data governance (38):

Health data is not only used for the benefit of the individual whose data is used but also commonly for the benefit of other individuals and the larger community. This is clear in the case of infectious diseases, as well as societal or environmental health threats where the use of data is of vital and urgent interest but also when developing prevention or treatment of other diseases. This requires balancing of various interests, in particular public health, and privacy. These public health purposes create a good basis for the acceptance of the secondary use in communities. Cross-border sharing of data can remarkably add to the power of data analysis and use.

To share and re-use AI-Mind data in the future, legal and ethical requirements must be considered, in addition to the platform where the data may be shared to. This chapter summarizes the regulations and guidelines for how to further sharing should be conducted and also maps the currently known opportunities for sharing of data.

3.1. Regulations and guidelines for sharing of data beyond AI-Mind

Once the collected data has been anonymised, then the GDPR does not apply to the data processing, cf. recital 26 of the GDPR (21).

If the personal data from AI-Mind is processed (in its pseudonymised form), for a purpose other than which it was collected, and not based on the data subjects consent or on a Union or Member State law (the GDPR Article 6 (4)), *the controller shall in order to ascertain whether processing for another purpose is compatible with the purpose for which the personal data are initially collected, take into account, inter alia:*

1. *any link between the purposes for which the personal data have been collected and the purposes of the intended further processing;*
2. *the context in which the personal data have been collected, in particular regarding the relationship between data subjects and the controller;*
3. *the nature of the personal data, in particular, whether special categories of personal data are processed,*
4. *the possible consequences of the intended further processing for data subjects;*
5. *the existence of appropriate safeguards, which may include encryption or pseudonymisation (16).*

Alongside the legislation, core values and factors that affect the willingness of data providers and controllers to share data that is curated and available on their data platforms was the subject of a recent quantitative study (39), summarised in Figure 3. Addressing solutions over credit and recognition, misinterpretation, loss of control, lack of resources and socioeconomic factors will contribute towards improving attitudes to data sharing.

Figure 3 Core values and factors that influence data sharing (39)

The FAIR data principles (that data should be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable to the greatest extent possible) offer an approach to enhance the usefulness of data. Converting FAIR from an ideology to a reality requires significant resources at each disciplinary level to develop data sharing and interoperability frameworks; with emphasis on legal and ethical principles and practices, as well as technical requirements relating to community agreed data formats, metadata standards, tools and data infrastructures (40).

It is envisaged that AI-Mind data will be shared to EU platforms like European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and / or EBRAINS. If and how this can be achieved will require further study of GDPR and national laws, as well as close alignment and agreements between AI-Mind partners, their DPOs and legal support. Further discussions within the AI-Mind consortium will be required to ensure that the utility and sustainability of data collected within AI-Mind can be achieved. Questions remain about the utility of anonymised health

data, the opinions of data owners, and what the alternative procedures will be if pseudonymised data is required. The questions require broad, balanced assessments of risk and benefit (balances of interest) and insight into the field of what is achieved by sharing the information on a sound basis. Risk and benefit assessments are a dynamic premise in legislation and in the GDPR.

3.2. Data sharing opportunities

3.2.1 European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)

**EUROPEAN OPEN
SCIENCE CLOUD**

Improving quality, efficiency and creativity can be achieved through open science. This requires the (often cross-border) sharing of knowledge, data, and tools between researchers, disciplines, institutes, and society.

Following its conception in 2016, a declaration of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and its principles was released in October 2017, addressing research data culture, services, architecture, governance and funding (41). EOSC is considered a process towards accelerating open science, FAIR data management and the use of digital methods and services, through cooperation, new insights and innovations, and improved productivity and reproducibility. The open, trusted, federation of infrastructure intends to enable approximately two million European researchers to store, share, discover, access, process, preserve, analyse, and reuse research digital objects.

AI-Mind intends to implement the central data repository (situated within the TSD Platform) in line with the EOSC principles through legally and ethically robust data sharing.

3.2.2 The Human Brain Project (HBP)

Human Brain Project

The Human Brain Project (HBP), co-funded by the European Union, was initiated in 2013 as one of three future and emerging technology flagship projects (42). The project has ongoing contributions from over 500 scientists and engineers at more than 140 universities, teaching hospitals and research centres across Europe: making it one of the largest research projects in the World.

The HBP is in its final phase from April 2020 to March 2023 to advance three core scientific areas on brain networks, their role in consciousness and artificial neural nets, whilst extending EBRAINS.

3.2.3 EBRAINS

EBRAINS

EBRAINS, created and funded through the extension of the HBP, represents a new sustainable era in Brain research (43). It aims to create a new international, cross-discipline digital research infrastructure that gathers an extensive range of data and tools to support brain-related research. The compilation of open (FAIR) state-of-the-art cutting-edge neuroscience, big data, computing, robotics, and related technologies will foster collaborative brain science and accelerate discovery for the benefit of patients and society. EBRAINS will also share expertise through the development of the Shared European Brain Research Agenda to culminate in the creation of the European partnership for Brain Health.

EBRAINS intends to secure Europe's digital leadership, underpinned by advances in the development of brain-inspired AI, neurorobotics and neuromorphic computing systems. This ambitious aim is supported by scale, organisation, tools, data resources, test facilities and use cases from collaborating advanced

neuro-scientific research. It also harnesses support from five leading supercomputing centres across Europe (Spain, France, Italy, Switzerland, and Germany).

Delivering on these aims and ambitions, EBRAINS has recently (June 2021) applied and been accepted into the 2021 Roadmap of the European strategy forum on Research infrastructures (ESFRI). Inclusion here is following a thorough selection procedure that encompasses evaluation of both scientific excellence and implementation rigour. *ESFRI's mission is to develop the scientific integration of Europe, to strengthen its international outreach, and to provide Europe with the most up-to-date Research Infrastructures, responding to the rapidly evolving Science frontiers, also advancing the knowledge-based technologies and their extended use. One of the core objectives of ESFRI is to ensure that excellent scientists have access to Europe's best research infrastructures irrespective of borders (44).*

EBRAINS data sets, to support continuous advancement of the field, are drawn from multiple sources within and externally to the HBP, and are curated to offer FAIR characteristics, accessible through EBRAINS *Knowledge Graph* services. From identification of relevant data, the *Knowledge Graph* provides a multi-modal metadata store, the linkage between experimental and neuroscientific data and a connection to software and hardware tools for analysis. In addition, *EBRAINS Atlases* (brain data exploration in 3D space), and the *EBRAINS Medical Informatics platform* (neurological clinical data from 30 hospitals representing 20,000 patients) provide FAIR access to data.

The security of such data is of primary concern, and as such a funding call for creation of a 'Service for Sensitive Data' was applied for (together with the HBP, April 2021 (45)) and successfully funded (September 2021), which will facilitate the processing of research participant data from the TSD Platform into the EBRAINS infrastructure (www.healthdatacloud.eu). This service intends to align with the European Health Data Space.

EBRAINS has a three-pillar objectives (46) broader in scope yet synergistic in approach to the aims of AI-Mind:

- Advance the scientific understanding of the brain
- Harness that subsequent understanding to deliver improved diagnosis and treatment of brain diseases
- Translate the improved knowledge of the brain into technological advances

3.2.4 HBP: EBRAINS voucher

AI-Mind will be integrated as an HBP partnering project, following a successful application with sister H2020 project TVB-Cloud to the EBRAINS service category 3 (SC3: Brain modelling and simulation workflows: integrated tools to create and investigate models of the brain). AI-Mind, in collaboration with TVB-Cloud, will compile EEG data and build computational models to be housed in EBRAINS. The proposal, providing finance for an engineer for 12 months to assist in data structuring, interoperability, and compatibility between AI-Mind and EBRAINS. AI-Mind will additionally benefit from EBRAINS data, expertise relating to TVB-Cloud infrastructure, legal knowledge, and opportunities arising from innovative research collaborations.

To improve the relevance of the data for future use, EBRAINS have stated a preference for the incorporation of pseudonymised data from AI-Mind. To deliver this, a forum amongst DPOs from AI-Mind's clinical partners has been set up to identify what legal bases and documentation are required for this to be achievable, with the identification of a necessity for DPIAs (October 2021).

3.2.5 The Virtual Brain Cloud

The Virtual Brain Cloud (TVB-cloud) aims to provide personalised prevention and treatment of dementia (47), from the creation of TVB simulator arising from the collation of large cohorts of patient and control data (in accordance with GDPR and EOSC). TVB-cloud will develop and validate a cloud-based environment that leverages the potential of big data and high-performance computing to prevent and treat neurodegenerative diseases, building on clinical expertise, computational biomedicine and integration.

4 Conclusions

The procedures that must be followed to enable the processing of health data within AI-Mind are complex, lengthy and often require multiple iterations to ensure that current and future data sharing is ethically approved and legally compliant.

Despite harmonisation of legislation (through the GDPR), there remain differences in interpretation as well as differing national requirements following interpretation of the GDPR into local legislation. Within AI-Mind these differences are highlighted by:

- The varying legal bases that the clinical partners use for data processing
- The role that consent plays (legal necessity – the GDPR, versus ethical requirement – the EDPB)
- The evolving discussions around the requirements for a DPIA
- The breadth of information contained within the consent forms.

Although these variations exist, they must be effectively navigated on a country and/or clinic level to ensure that they do not act prohibitively to prevent progress within AI-Mind.

To prevent siloing of valuable data: future data processing methods and standardised procedures must be developed and embraced to streamline access to research health data. This will enable the future of science to generate increased value from preexisting resources.

5 Acknowledgements

This work is a collaboration with valuable input from all partners in the project, specifically the clinical partners within AI-Mind that provided the country/clinic specific information required.

6 References

1. The International Organization for Standardization. ISO 25237:2017 Health informatics — Pseudonymization [Internet]. 1st ed. 2017. 62 p. Available from: <https://www.iso.org/standard/63553.html>
2. The European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. General Data Protection Regulation - article 4 [Internet]. via Intersoft Consulting. Available from: <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-4-gdpr/>
3. The European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data [Internet]. European Union and EEA; 2016. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>
4. The European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. REGULATION (EU) 2016/679 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL [Internet]. EU; 2016 p. 88. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679>
5. The commission to the European Parliament. Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council “Laying down harmonised rules on Artificial intelligence (ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ACT) and amending certain union legislative acts” [Internet]. 2021 p. 108. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021PC0206>
6. World Medical Association. Declaration of Helsinki: Ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects [Internet]. Available from: <https://www.wma.net/policies-post/wma-declaration-of-helsinki-ethical-principles-for-medical-research-involving-human-subjects/>
7. US Food and drug agency. Code of Federal Regulations Title 21 subpart 56 [Internet]. Available from: <https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/scripts/cdrh/cfdocs/cfcfr/CFRSearch.cfm?CFRPart=56>
8. US Food and drug agency. Code of Federal Regulations Title 21 subpart 312 [Internet]. Available from: <https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/scripts/cdrh/cfdocs/cfcfr/CFRSearch.cfm?CFRPart=312>
9. WHO, UNESCO. Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences [Internet]. Available from: <https://cioms.ch/>
10. De Panfilis L, Merlo DF, Satolli R, Perin M, Ghirotto L, Costantini M. Clinical ethics consultation among Italian ethics committee: A mixed method study. PLoS One [Internet]. 2020 Dec 30;14(12):e0226710. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0226710>
11. Ministry of Social Affairs and Health F. Medical Research Act [Internet]. 2010 p. 13. Available from: <https://www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/1999/en19990488.pdf>
12. Juan Carlos I. Biomedical Research [Internet]. Spain; p. 48. Available from: <https://www.isciii.es/QueHacemos/Financiacion/solicitudes/Documents/SpanishLawonBiomedicalResearchEnglish.pdf>
13. The Norwegian Ministry of Health and Care Services. Health Research Act [Internet]. Norway; 2008. Available from: <https://lovdata.no/dokument/NL/lov/2008-06-20-44>
14. The Norwegian National Research Ethics Committees. The Health Research Act [Internet]. 2020. Available from: <https://www.forskningsetikk.no/en/resources/the-research-ethics-library/legal-statutes-and-guidelines/the-health-research-act/>
15. The European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Directive 95/46/EC of the

- European Parliament and of the Council of 24 October 1995 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data [Internet]. 95/46/EU 1995. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A31995L0046>
16. The European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. General Data Protection Regulation - chapter 2 [Internet]. via Intersoft Consulting. EU; Available from: <https://gdpr-info.eu/chapter-2/>
 17. The European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. General Data Protection Regulation - chapter 4 [Internet]. via Intersoft Consulting. Available from: <https://gdpr-info.eu/chapter-4/>
 18. Data2.EU. What is a DPIA - Data Protection Impact Assessment? [Internet]. Available from: <https://data2.eu/en/gdpr/what-is-a-dpia>
 19. Article 29 Data Protection Working Party. Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is “likely to result in a high risk” for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679 [Internet]. 2017. Available from: https://autoriteitpersoonsgegevens.nl/sites/default/files/atoms/files/20171013_wp248_rev01_en.pdf.pdf
 20. The European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. General Data Protection Regulations - chapter 9 [Internet]. via Intersoft Consulting. Available from: <https://gdpr-info.eu/chapter-9/>
 21. The European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. General Data Protection Regulation - recital 26 [Internet]. via Intersoft Consulting. Available from: <https://gdpr-info.eu/recitals/no-26/>
 22. European Data Protection Board. EDPB Document on response to the request from the European Commission for clarifications on the consistent application of the GDPR, focusing on health research [Internet]. 2021 p. 14. Available from: https://edpb.europa.eu/sites/default/files/files/file1/edpb_replyec_questionnaire_research_final.pdf
 23. European Data Protection Board. Guidelines 05/2020 on consent under Regulation 2016/679 [Internet]. 2020 p. 33. Available from: https://edpb.europa.eu/sites/default/files/files/file1/edpb_guidelines_202005_consent_en.pdf
 24. European Data Protection Board. Opinion 3/2019 concerning the Questions and Answers on the interplay between the Clinical Trials Regulation (CTR) and the General Data Protection regulation (GDPR) [Internet]. 2019. Available from: https://edpb.europa.eu/sites/default/files/files/file1/edpb_opinionctrq_a_final_en.pdf
 25. The European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. DIRECTIVE (EU) 2016/680 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection [Internet]. 2016 p. 43. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32016L0680>
 26. The European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. REGULATION (EU) 2018/1725 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 23 October 2018 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by the Union institutions, bodies, offices and agencies and on the free movement [Internet]. Official Journal of the European Union;

- 2018 p. 60. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32018R1725>
27. Italian Ministry. ITALIAN PERSONAL DATA PROTECTION CODE [Internet]. Italy; 2003. Available from: <http://www.privacy.it/archivio/privacycode-en.html>
 28. Jones Day. Italian Data Protection Decree Harmonizes National Law with GDPR Provisions [Internet]. Insights. 2018. Available from: <https://www.jonesday.com/en/insights/2018/10/italian-data-protection-decree-harmonizes-national/>
 29. Ministry of Social Affairs and Health. Medical Research Act [Internet]. Finland; 1999. Available from: <https://www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/1999/en19990488.pdf>
 30. Finnish Parliament. Data Protection Act [Internet]. Finland; 2018. Available from: <https://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/alkup/2018/20181050>
 31. Ministry of Social Affairs and Health. Act on the Status and Rights of Patients [Internet]. Finland; 1992. Available from: https://www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/1992/en19920785_20120690.pdf
 32. Ministry of Social Affairs and Health Finland. Secondary use of health and social data [Internet]. 2019. Available from: <https://stm.fi/en/secondary-use-of-health-and-social-data>
 33. Carlos J, Garmendia Mendizábal C. [Royal Decree 1716/2011, dated November 18, establishing the basic requirements of authorization and functioning of biobanks for biomedical research and the management of human biological samples, and regulating the functioning and organization of the Na. Rev derecho y genoma Hum = Law Hum genome Rev. 2012;(36):209–33.
 34. Requejo MT. Legal analysis of the Spanish Basic Law 41/2002 on the autonomy of the patient and the rights and obligations with regard to clinical information and documentation. Eur J Health Law. 2003 Sep;10(3):257–69.
 35. Head of state S. Ley 33/2011, de 4 de octubre, General de Salud Pública. [Internet]. 2011 p. 34. Available from: <https://www.boe.es/eli/es/l/2011/10/04/33>
 36. PB Juridico. The Organic Law 3/2018, of December 5, on Data Protection and Guarantee of Digital Rights enters into force [Internet]. 2019. Available from: <https://www.pbjuridico.com/the-organic-law-3-2018-of-december-5-on-data-protection-and-guarantee-of-digital-rights-enters-into-force-2/?lang=en#:~:text=Uncategorized-,The Organic Law 3%2F2018%2C of December 5%2C on,Digital Rights enters into force&text=Th>
 37. Norway M of E. The Research Ethics Act [Internet]. 2018. Available from: <https://www.regjeringen.no/no/dokumenter/forskningsetikkloven/id426515/>
 38. Towards European Health Data Space. Why health is a special case for data governance [Internet]. 2021. Available from: <https://tehdas.eu/app/uploads/2021/06/tehdas-why-health-is-a-special-case-for-data-governance-2021-06-23.pdf>
 39. Devriendt T, Borry P, Shabani M. Factors that influence data sharing through data sharing platforms: A qualitative study on the views and experiences of cohort holders and platform developers. PLoS One [Internet]. 2021 Jul 2;16(7):e0254202. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0254202>
 40. European Commission Expert group on FAIR data. Turning FAIR into reality [Internet]. 2018. Available from: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/turning_fair_into_reality_1.pdf
 41. EOSC stakeholder signatories. EOSC declaration [Internet]. 2017. Available from: https://eosc-portal.eu/sites/default/files/eosc_declaration.pdf

42. Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Lausanne. Human Brain Project [Internet]. Available from: <https://www.humanbrainproject.eu/en/>
43. EBRAINS [Internet]. Available from: <https://ebrains.eu/services>
44. Peter Zekert. EBRAINS selected for the ESFRI Roadmap of European Research Infrastructures [Internet]. 2021. Available from: <https://ebrains.eu/news/ebrains-selected-for-esfri-roadmap/>
45. EBRAINS. Human Brain Project and EBRAINS launch call to build services for sensitive data [Internet]. 2021. Available from: <https://ebrains.eu/news/Human-Brain-Project-EBRAINS-launch-call-to-build-services-for-sensitive-data>
46. Discover EBRAINS [Internet]. Available from: <https://ebrains.eu/discover>
47. Germany CU-. Virtual Brain Cloud [Internet]. Available from: <https://virtualbraincloud-2020.eu/tvb-cloud-main.html>

Appendix - DTA variations between partners

Table 3 DTA variations and similarities – the red text lists the differences explicitly, the green text indicates agreement between all four DTAs.

	IRCCS	HUS	UCM	UCSC	Green indicates same text for
Pages	6	6	7 (page 7 is blank)	6	
Clases					
Clause 1 Practical terms of transfer....	1.8 The recipient will reimburse the provider for its costs of shipping the material in the amount of NOK. The provider will arrange the shipping of the material to the recipient and will be responsible for the material until the material is delivered	1.8 The recipient will reimburse the provider for its costs of shipping the material in the amount of NOK. The provider will arrange the shipping of the material to the recipient and will be responsible for the material until the material is delivered	1.2 i ii iii - do not specify article 5 GDPR processing, just say GDPR		1.1 1.2 i ii iii 1.3 1.4 1.5 1.6 1.7
Clause 2 confidentiality			2.1 i ii - The specific measures to warranty this compromise are specified in Appendix 2 iii iv v vi vii viii 2.2 i ii iii iv v vi		2.1 i ii iii iv v vi vii viii 2.2 i ii iii iv v vi 2.3
Clause 3 IP	Follow CA for AI Mind	Follow CA for AI Mind	Follow CA for AI Mind	Follow CA for AI Mind	Follow CA for AI
Clause 4 Publication	Follow CA for AI Mind	Follow CA for AI Mind	Follow CA for AI Mind - if scientific results are published together with the data object of this agreement, such data must be published in an irreversible anonymized form to preserve participant confidentiality	Follow CA for AI Mind	Edits for UCM
Clause 5 Liability	Follow CA for AI Mind	Follow CA for AI Mind	Follow CA for AI Mind	Follow CA for AI Mind	Follow CA for AI
Clause 6 General provisions					6.1 6.2 6.3 6.4
Clause 7 Duration and termination					7.1 7.2 7.3 7.4
Clause 8 Duty to confirm compliance and allow audits					8.1 8.2
Clause 9 Transfer of rights and renegotiation					9.1 9.2
Clause 10 Governing law and jurisdiction	Follow CA for AI Mind	Follow CA for AI Mind	This agreement shall be governed by Spanish law and jurisdictions and the tribunals in Madrid shall have exclusive right to deal with any dispute which may arise out of or in connection with this agreement	Follow CA for AI Mind	Edits for UCM
Clause 11 Notices	11.1 11.2	11.1 11.2	11.1 11.2	11.1 11.2	11.1 11.2
Clause 12 Data protection		Follow CA for AI Mind	Follow CA for AI Mind		UCSC and IRCCS have no clause 12
Appendix 1	Bibliography	Bibliography	no bibliography Appendix 2 TSD WP v6.0Des2019	Bibliography	Research protocol in the document protocol